

IDEA: Incorporating Diversity into the Evaluation and Assessment of Researchers

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FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO THE LEAKY PIPELINE PHENOMENON

	Factors	Suggestion solutions
1	Lack of clear and transparent promotion criteria	Transparent, unambiguous and well-communicated promotion criteria
2	Disproportionally high workloads of invisible service work	Equal distribution of labor
3	Sexism and racial discrimination	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Acknowledge identity in knowledge production over 'objectivity'• Promote inclusivity, diversity, and equity through policies and trainings, and monitor• Role models
4	Exclusion from professional and support networks	Culturally competent mentorship
5	Precarious working conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Support for parents and caretakers• Do not expect uniform productivity
6	Lack of (financial) support for engaging in true research interests.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Provide growth possibilities• Reward and value research on diversity, equity and inclusion

*Findings from literature review

QUESTIONS TO EXPLORE

2

- How attractive is VU as an employer for different demographic and professional groups?
- Will the proposed changes meaningfully impact the balance between valuing teaching and research?
- To what extent do ambiguous promotion criteria pose a barrier to achieving diversity?
- How do current criteria limit mobility and interdisciplinarity within VU?
- Why is there no specific targeting of PhD candidates or Team Science initiatives, and what are the implications?

*Findings from workshop #1 IDEA

MAPPING DIVERSITY WITHIN FACULTY POLICIES

BETA: Diversity is explicitly stated as a goal, but no explanation of what it entails. The policy mentions actions like bias training, diverse committees, and inclusive recruitment practices.

CENT: Diversity is addressed in relation to different research profiles, with much discussion around horizontal growth in academia and transitions to management support roles. However, most of this is not reflected in the faculty policies.

1

Diversity addressed in policies?

BETA: Faculty of Science
ACTA: Faculty of Dentistry
SOC: School of Social Sciences
HUM: School of Humanities
MED: Faculty of Medicine
LAW: Faculty of Law
SBE: School of Business and Economics
REL: School of Religion
FMBS: Faculty of Behavioral and Movement Sciences
CENT: Central Policy

BETA: There are many criteria, but it's not always clear how they're balanced. Mention of clear red flags.

ACTA: Includes examples for five categories, with checkboxes showing what's expected at each level — Junior, Medior, Senior, and Expert.

SOC: Mention of service work for all profiles and positions.

HUM: Procedure to become a full professor is missing, as it's covered elsewhere. Salary scales are included.

REL: Detailed criteria but subjective and open to interpretation.

Policy developers known?

2

Clear and transparent criteria?

3

Research
Teaching
Impact
Leadership
Care/
Management

ACTA: Rubrics should be developed with narratives where staff explain leaves taken. Not clear whether this affects evaluation.

SBE: Female employees receive six months' exemption from teaching after maternity leave; male employees are not required to make up teaching missed during childbirth leave.

Consideration of care-taking roles

5

Committee diversity addressed?

4

OTHER CONSIDERATIONS

- Most policies mention a mix of qualitative and quantitative indicators.
- There is an underlying assumption that everyone should aim for vertical growth from UD2-UD1-UHD2-UHD2-HL
- BETA policy mentions equal division of tasks among staff with concrete suggestions.
- SOC policy explicitly mentions and rewards service work for all profiles and positions.
- SOC, HUM and REL are now Schools within the Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities.

Note: The central policy (CENT) is intended as a guiding framework. Faculties have been tasked with translating it into their own concrete policies.

Addressed
 Ambiguous
 Not addressed